

Digital transformation of Ethnolinguistic Maps of Eastern Lithuania

Giedrė Beconytė², Linas Bevainis², Lina Semokaitė, and Vilius Talkevičius¹

¹ Institute of Geosciences, Vilnius University, Vilnius, Lithuania

Correspondence: Giedrė Beconytė (giedre.beconyte@gf.vu.lt)

Abstract. This map is based on a historical and geographical analysis of the ethnolinguistic development in eastern Lithuania, conducted nearly 30 years ago by cartographer Petras Gaučas (1942–2000). The primary source material for this map includes a publication derived from Gaučas's doctoral dissertation, published in 2004 and now regarded as a bibliographic rarity, along with original hand-drawn research materials. The project resulted in a single map illustrating ethnolinguistic processes in eastern Lithuania from the 17th century to 1939. This map and the underlying GIS database were created through the analysis, digitisation, and processing of the materials. Although the work required significant time and additional analysis, the outcome demonstrates how modern technologies can effectively enhance the understanding of research findings preserved through older methods, thereby ensuring their continued usability.

Submission Type. Case study.

BoK Concepts. [DM4] Vector data model, Feature-based modelling, Applications; [CV5] Map production.

Keywords. Ethnolinguistic, map, spatial database, reconstruction, Eastern Lithuania

1 Background

A map of the ethnolinguistic development of the inhabitants of Eastern Lithuania, based on historical and geographical research of the cartographer Petras Gaučas (1942–2000), is presented. This was the first comprehensive study to combine ethnic, linguistic, and religious aspects of the development of the language and the self-awareness of the inhabitants of eastern Lithuania, a region with a complex history. P. Gaučas examined in detail the eastern and southern borders of the Lithuanian ethnic territory over a period of more than 300 years, from the 17th century to 1939. Based on data on Baltic and Slavic oikonyms and the religion of the population, which he collected from various historical sources and during live expeditions, he showed how the territorial spread of the Lithuanian language changed over time. The synthesis of ethnolinguistic processes in Eastern Lithuania is a

historical-geographical model of the region's development, revealing the reasons for the current ethnic and linguistic composition of the population impacted by the Slavicization process during the following periods:

- a) the years of the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth (Republic);
- b) the years of Tsarist Russian rule; and
- c) the years of Polish occupation in the Vilnius region.

Figure 1. The boundaries of the Lithuanian-speaking areas, created by P. Gaučas, drawn on a cartographic base using graphical editing software in ca. 2000.

The cartographic results gave these studies particular value. Unfortunately, the detailed maps were prepared using digital graphics software or by hand rather than GIS (Fig. 1). Therefore, the data presented in them could not be used for further analysis. Given the importance of the research data to the academic communities of historians, geographers, and linguists, it was decided to digitise the maps and to create a consistent GIS database.

2 Methods

2.1 Data Processing and Mapping

The main challenges in digitising the research results in the GIS database were:

- Interpretive maps drawn by hand on various cartographic backgrounds, lacking detailed information about their coordinate system and accuracy;
- Different map scales and periods depicted;
- The diversity of objects (areas, points, statistical diagrams).

Therefore, it was necessary not only to link the maps with coordinates but also to vectorise objects, standardise attributes, and perform cartographic generalisation based on the accuracy of the original maps. The data from the old maps was critically evaluated, systematised, and inaccuracies were corrected. Spatial data from the national georeferenced cadastre and *OpenStreetMap* were used to refine the locations of settlements and other objects. Statistical information was reconstructed from available data in manuscripts, and where this was lacking, some was recalculated from hand-drawn percentage diagrams.

The georeferencing error using the 1st order polynomial transformation method ranged from 5.95 m in the northern part of the territory to 6.66 m in the southern part. The data topology for the Slavicization processes was corrected – overlaps and gaps caused by inaccuracies were eliminated.

Digital data layers were created by combining information from several maps.

1. Ethnolinguistic territories,
2. Churches and languages of worship in 1939,
3. Non-governmental Lithuanian educational institutions in 1919–1939,
4. Administrative boundaries.

A single map was created covering all these layers. A lot of work went into creating a new, more modern-looking system of cartographic symbols that better reflects the complexity of the map objects, is semantically more correct, and visually retains the appearance of the original maps. The map has been supplemented with newly created diagrams and an inset map comparing the ethnic composition of the population in 1857 and 1919.

2.2 Data and Software Availability

ArcGIS Pro and *QGIS* software were used to create the database and to compile the map. Once the map is published, the full spatial data set will be made available for unrestricted Internet access on the National Open

Access Research Data Archive (MIDAS, <https://www.midas.lt/>).

3 Results

The final result of the project is a map and a GIS database that combine the boundaries of Slavicization processes in Eastern Lithuania with the factors that influenced them: administrative boundaries, ethnic composition, educational institutions, and the language of worship in churches (Fig. 2). This is data of great enduring value, reflecting the complex and controversial process of change in the language and self-identity of the inhabitants of eastern Lithuania. Presented in a modern format, it helps explore a problem at the intersection of several academic disciplines and at the crossroads of the interests of different nations, cultures, and states.

Conclusion

Although by the year 2000 some of the results of valuable cartographic research had already been preserved in digital form, they are not easily reusable and may therefore be lost altogether.

Transferring old maps into modern GIS databases and maps requires significant effort and time, but it is worth doing, especially if the research is interdisciplinary. The resulting open data can be used by other researchers, students, local historians, and even policymakers

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that they have used Generative AI tools in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, the AI tools were used for language editing, not for generating content, research data, or conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors without AI assistance.

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our gratitude to Petras Gaučas' family for their generosity in sharing the materials from his original research.

References

Gaučas, P. *Etnolingvistinė Rytų Lietuvos gyventojų raida (XVII a. antroji pusė–1939 m.)/ Ethnolinguistic development of the population of Eastern Lithuania (second half of the 17th century–1939)*. Ph.D. thesis, Vilnius: Vilnius University, 19

